

Improved Linearity of Power Amplifier GaN MMIC For Ka-Band SATCOM

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Abstract — The linearity performance of a Ka-band power amplifier (PA) GaN MMIC with a novel balanced 4-way combiner is presented. The 32 – 38 GHz two-stage PA produces a maximum power of 6 watts for class-A bias. Improved linearity is demonstrated by biasing the first and second stages in deep class AB, and class A, respectively. This improvement in overall linearity is achieved as the gain expansion of the first stage is balanced by the gain compression of the second stage. Measured linearity performance is presented.

Index Terms — intermodulation distortion, GaN MMIC.

I. INTRODUCTION

The higher data rates required for satellite communication links continue to drive the frequency of operation towards millimeter-wave (mmW) frequencies for both commercial and defense satellite applications [1], [2]. The availability of high-power, high-efficiency, linear amplifiers at these frequencies is important for the successful deployment of these systems. Traditional traveling-wave-tube amplifiers (TWTAs) [3] are being replaced with wide-bandgap semiconductor devices. GaN on SiC high-electron mobility transistors (HEMTs) and monolithic microwave integrated circuits (MMICs) have been demonstrated at mmW frequencies with power densities which are an order of magnitude higher than those from earlier technologies [4]. The GaN on SiC technology has showed continuous improvements in output power, efficiency, bandwidth, and reliability [5].

The use of GaN technology at mmW frequencies has witnessed a significant increase in the past few years starting from devices with record power densities to high-performance MMICs with excellent bandwidth (1–50 GHz [6], and 2–20 GHz [7]), high power [5], and high levels of integration [8]. The GaN technology's performance has led to its consideration for many applications in which linearity and efficiency are critical. Recent efforts have focused on improving linearity [9] and efficiency [10] of GaN amplifiers. One of the challenges in PA design is achieving high linearity without degrading efficiency. This paper presents a PA MMIC with a novel balanced 4-way combiner, and a built-in linearity improvement mechanism. The MMIC combines four two-stage PAs using a balanced 4-way combiner. Linearity improvements can be achieved through biasing the first and second stages in deep class AB, and class A, respectively. This technique balances the gain expansion of the first stage with the gain compression of the second stage resulting in

higher IP3. Linearity data for two tone, and digitally modulated input signals are presented.

II. LINEARITY CHARACTERIZATION AND IMPROVEMENT

Improving the linearity of a PA can be achieved through the *balanced-AB* class of operation [11]. In that reference, the linearity of a single stage amplifier was improved by biasing the HEMT in deep class AB such that the gain expansion (at low input drive levels) is balanced by the gain compression (at high input drive levels) resulting in reduced gain compression (versus input drive level). However, the same concept can be extended to a two-stage amplifier, as shown here. In a two-stage amplifier, the first stage can be biased in deep class AB to produce gain expansion which balances out the gain compression of the second stage. This results in reduced amplitude-modulation to amplitude-modulation (AM-AM) and amplitude-modulation to phase-modulation (AM-PM) conversion and improved linearity.

III. MEASURED RESULTS AND LINEARITY CHARACTERIZATION

The GaN MMIC was implemented in a 0.25 μm gate process. The MMIC had an output stage with 3.2 mm total gate periphery, see Fig. 1. The PA combines 4 two-stage amplifiers through a novel balanced combiner. The MMIC was eutectically die-attached to a test-fixture for efficient heat removal (Fig. 2). The gain and output power versus input power are shown on Fig. 3. The saturated output power is about 6 watts.

Fig. 1. Picture of fabricated MMIC PA.

Fig. 2. Packaged GaN MMIC PA.

Fig. 3. Output power and gain versus input power at 32.5 GHz, 35 V drain voltage.

The linearity was measured using a custom millimeter-wave digital waveform system. A detailed description of the system was given in [11]. The system is capable of generating and analyzing wide range of waveforms including single-tone, two-tone and digitally modulated waveforms up to 50 GHz.

All of the measurements were carried out in the Ka-band at 32.5 GHz, and the drain voltage for all amplifier stages was set at 32 V. Furthermore, the gate biases of the first stages in all the parallel branches were provided by a single supply and the gate bias of the second stages were provide by another power supply.

The measured two-tone intermodulation products (IMDs) are shown in Fig. 4. The total drain currents in all the first stages and all the second stages are 0.506 A and 0.777 A, respectively.

The amplifier was also tested with different digitally modulated waveforms (QPSK, OQPSK, 16QAM, and 32QAM). All the waveforms had a symbol rate of 10 MSymbols/s, and were filtered by identical matching root-raised-cosine filters with a roll-off factor of 0.4 in the transmitter and the receiver. The total bandwidth of the input waveforms was therefore 14 MHz. In Fig. 5, EVM is plotted as a function of output power and ACPR is shown in Fig. 6. The center of the adjacent channel is defined to be 1.5 symbol rate (15 MHz) away from the center of the main channel. Note the advantage of OQPSK with respect to spectral growth as

shown in Fig. 6. The lower ACPR for OQPSK is caused by the elimination of zero-crossing in the waveform.

The transfer characteristics of a millimeter-wave GaN HEMT have been shown to have strong dependence on the drain current bias [11]. It is therefore reasonable to suggest that, by adjusting the drain current biases for the first and the second stages separately, optimized linearity can be achieved. One scenario is to bias the first stage in deep class-AB mode of operation and the second-stage in class A. The gain expansion in the first stage deep class AB amplifier is used to balance the gain compression of the second stage class A amplifier and an overall improvement in linearity can be achieved. In Fig. 7, the measured ACPR is shown for three different first stage drain current biases (in Ampere): 0.506 (class A), 0.076 (deep class AB), and 0.014 (class B). The drain current for the second stage was set to 0.777 A (class A) for all three measurements. The linearity advantage of the combination of deep class AB in the first stage and class A in the second stage is evident. This linearization concept can be extended, with more operational flexibility, to three-stage amplifiers.

Fig. 4. Measured two-tone IMDs of the amplifier.

Fig. 5. Measured EVM of the amplifier.

Fig. 6. Measured ACPR of the amplifier.

Fig. 7. Measured ACPR of the amplifier for different biases of the first-stage drain current.

IV. CONCLUSION

A four-way, balanced MMIC PA with improved linearity was presented in the Ka-band. The 32 – 38 GHz two-stage PA produces about 6 watts at the frequency of linearization study. It utilizes the *balanced-AB* class to improve the linearity. Linearity improvement data for two tone, and digitally modulated input signals were presented.

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